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Using Clinical Pathways To Virtual Coach Elderly For Home Rehabilitation

Completed Research Paper

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Abstract

When transitioning from the hospital to the home context, elderly patients need motivation and help to engage in rehabilitation. Prior research supposes Virtual Coaches (VCs) to keep motivated and to serve as a companion. Yet, using VCs for home rehabilitation requires various technologies (e.g., smart sensors and machine learning) and stakeholders. In this paper, we report about a case study as part of the vCare project on using clinical pathways to set the procedural precept for integrating diverse technologies and stakeholders for home rehabilitation. We contribute to design artifacts and to design knowledge. For design knowledge, we systemize requirements that help design further modeling languages for modeling clinical pathways, derive further clinical pathways, or integrate further technologies or stakeholders in supervised care. Furthermore, our design artifacts may be used to investigate research ideas of other IS domains such as gamification or anthropomorphism.

Keywords: Virtual Coaching, Clinical Pathway, Conceptual Modeling, BPMN

Introduction

Every sixth person living in the European Union has a disability (Jarlath 2011). Especially older patients are prone to disabilities (Bethge et al. 2014) and need time to regain their independence and quality of life in a rehabilitation period (Parker et al. 2009). For these patients, rehabilitation usually continues after transitioning from hospital to home, with continuity of care often being interrupted. Although solutions exist (e.g., Electronic Medical Records; EMR) that help physicians coordinate care activities for a patient beyond the hospital setting, these solutions do not support the patient himself with domestic rehabilitation activities. To ensure continuity of care, prior research rather suggests employing Virtual Coaches (VCs; Ding et al. 2010; Kyriazakos et al. 2020) as an interactive virtual human (Diederich et al. 2020) that engages in conversation (Cassell 2000; Diederich et al. 2020) with the patient. VCs allow fostering physical activities, monitoring vital signs, setting incentives to promote activities, and supporting user's health literacy (Kyriazakos et al. 2020). They also serve as a companion whose guidance is trusted (Allen et al. 2008). Yet, to be used as a tool for fostering home rehabilitation, VCs need to fulfill various requirements. First, the VCs' actions need to adhere to clinical guidelines, which describe recommended activities for the medical team and patients (Field and Lohr 1990), and also need to integrate personalized instructions given by caregivers to individualize care for the patient (Kyriazakos et al. 2020). Second, data from smart-home and self-monitoring sensors need to be integrated so that caregivers can choose actions or schedule unplanned examinations. Third, a virtual coach also needs to learn from prior recommendations (e.g., a daily fitness program) and the patient's outcome (e.g., program completed/avoided; impact on vital signs) to provide optimal future recommendations. To fulfill these requirements, various technologies are required,

including smart-home and self-monitoring sensors, machine learning, and clinical pathways that allow for constantly updating and personalizing the patient's care plan (see Figure 1). Prior research has already combined individual technologies such as touch screen interfaces, electronic textual reminders, adaptive avatars, or wearables (Tropea et al. 2019). Yet, integrating diverse technologies is still challenging. Without integrating technologies such as smart-home and self-monitoring sensors, physicians cannot sufficiently monitor their patients and react if needed, and without integrating a machine learning component, the VC cannot adapt to the patient's behavior, such as a tendency to skip disliked tasks.

Figure 1. Relevant Technologies To Fully Exploit The Potential Of VCs For The Home Rehabilitation Of Elderly

Integrating diverse technologies requires a technology that sets the procedural precepts and defines when to use and integrate the other technologies. We think that clinical pathways are an appropriate technology to do so. Clinical pathways are used primarily at the organizational level of medical facilities (Kinsman et al. 2010; Panella and Vanhaecht 2010) and include standardized descriptions of clinical processes for defined combinations of symptoms adapted to the specific clinical conditions (de Bleser et al. 2006). Over time, clinical pathways evolved as a process-oriented tool, involving coordinated care (de Bleser et al. 2006; Kinsman et al. 2010), including different medical stakeholders and the patient and hence, enabled continuous treatment with multiple caregivers (Lenz and Reichert 2007). Prior research has investigated the effectiveness of clinical pathways and reports a decreasing length of hospital stays and better coordination of the care procedure (Rotter 2013; Rotter et al. 2010). However, clinical pathways often remain on an organizational level as a textual or plain document. Although examples exist in which clinical pathways are integrated into the daily work routines, they relate to restricted scenarios (e.g., special hospitals or departments (Burwitz et al. 2012; Neame et al. 2019)) and their integration into IT systems can best be described as struggling. Evolving clinical pathways to set the procedural precept for integrating different technologies may help to a) integrate clinical pathways into the daily work routines and b) to enable a complex VC scenario to guide patients at home. This paper reports on the design of a modeling language, a modeling tool, and clinical pathways used in the *vCare project* to integrate various technologies to design personalized rehabilitation programs that envisage a better continuity of care and quality of life for patients using a VC. Our contributions are twofold. For practice, we contribute three types of design artifacts (modeling language, modeling tool, clinical pathways) that can be directly applied for home rehabilitation scenarios. For theory, we contribute to the design knowledge base by systemizing requirements, design decisions, and methodological implications to guide future researchers to i) design further domain-specific modeling languages for similar scenarios, ii) design further clinical pathways for VC-guided rehabilitation, and iii) to integrate other technologies or stakeholders.

Method

Design Science Research (DSR) has emerged as an essential research paradigm, contributing to theory and practice to solve real-world problems (vom Brocke et al. 2020). During the last years, DSR has made significant progress resulting in concrete guidance to help formulate research goals and structure work (vom Brocke et al. 2020; Gregor and Hevner 2013; Hevner et al. 2004). This paper follows the DSR approach by Kuechler and Vaishnavi (2008), who propose a high-level design process followed by various design science methods. In this design process, awareness of the problem is raised, and a potential solution is suggested. Then, requirements are described, and the artifact is developed and evaluated (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Research Design As A Combination Of DSR And Multiple Case Study

Having described the need for VC-guided home rehabilitation for the elderly and the solution of clinical pathways that set the procedural precept for integrating different technologies and stakeholders, we now specify how such a solution can be conceptualized. Prior research has suggested business process models as a means for modeling clinical pathways to enable understanding for different stakeholders (Stark et al. 2016) and to secure formalization (Burwitz et al. 2013; Heß et al. 2015). Typical business process models such as the Business Process Modeling and Notation (BPMN) and the Event-driven Process Chain (EPC) capture tasks, events, states, and flow logic (Reijers and Mendling 2011). However, these process modeling languages do not yet function as a basis for informing a VC by bridging different technologies and stakeholders. This is why we investigate requirements to adapt clinical pathways to bridge different technologies and stakeholders and hence, allow for a complex virtual coaching scenario necessary for home rehabilitation. Having investigated requirements, we develop the modeling language based on those languages that best fulfill the requirements, the corresponding modeling tool, and the clinical pathways and evaluate the artifacts. To investigate requirements and design and evaluate the artifacts, we combine this DSR-project with a multiple case study. This combination allows for integrating different health problems relevant to the rehabilitation processes of the elderly. Furthermore, it allows for agile development with frequent interaction between potential users and developers (Madsen and Matook 2010; Maruping and Matook 2020; Matook et al. 2016).

Case Overview

The case study, according to (Mason 2017; Yin 2014), includes three cases so that multi-faceted concepts of a diverse range of health issues relevant for the home rehabilitation of the elderly are covered within the vCare project with a focus on cardiologic and neurologic pathologies. As use cases, we integrated departments of three clinics (in the following termed clinic 1-3):

Clinic 1 is one of Romania's most important medical academic institutions, with about 10,000 students and 37 affiliated clinics, including several hundreds of hospital beds. For the present case, the focus is on cardiologic pathologies like heart failure diminishing the patients' vitality and capability to take care of their own life. For these pathologies, clinic 1 has an integrated department for treating cardiovascular diseases that includes an emergency ward having a total of 62 beds. The person in charge and principal investigator is a local research physician of the clinic, focusing on cardiac rehabilitation.

Clinic 2 is settled in the northwest of Spain and is the principal university hospital of the regional healthcare system. The clinic has a target population of 370,000 persons in basic care. It is the referee hospital for complex and specialized care units in the region and reaches more than 2 million people. There are 867 beds and 35 operating rooms. Clinic 2 and its Movement Disorders and Autonomic Disorders Unit is integrated for the treatment of Parkinson's disease as a non-acute neurological pathology. Here, the primary need is for patients to cope with the increasing number of impairments.

Clinic 3 is settled in the north of Italy. It is a fully integrated multi-specialty private clinical center that provides inpatient and outpatient services mainly directed to neurological patients. The focus in terms of the case study is on stroke as an acute neurological disease mainly causing movement- and sensory-related impairments that require rehabilitation to re-obtain independence and quality of life. The relevant center is a 136-bed rehabilitation clinic plus a 12-bed day hospital facility.

Data Collection

Data were collected between November 2018 and October 2020. To identify the requirements for the design artifacts, we have applied a two-step procedure: In the first step, we have used a role game across all cases to foster understanding of the VC process and the interrelationships between the stakeholders (Korhonen et al. 2007). Furthermore, we aimed to identify the disease-independent information that needs to be handled in clinical pathways. In a second step, we have specified the requirements for disease-dependent information for cardiovascular diseases, Parkinson's disease, and stroke. Therefore, all clinics specified information that needed to be included within the clinical pathways as a prosaic description, which we have analyzed and further used to formulate disease-dependent requirements. Subsequently, we conducted a first round of interviews to ensure that information was understood appropriately and to identify further relevant information. The interviews were conducted with 1-3 participants per clinic depending on the particular field of expertise of the participant. Furthermore, we organized an overview session with the clinics to discuss overarching issues. Based on the resulting requirements, we started a build-evaluate stage according to Sonnenberg and vom Brocke (2012) with two build-evaluate cycles. The first build-evaluate cycle includes the implementation of the modeling language, tool, and clinical pathways. Afterwards, the first results could be discussed with clinical experts using interviews (second round). Each interview session followed a "narrating" or "re-narrating" approach, meaning that we directly discussed with the clinicians whether elements of the pathway had been understood correctly. Potential changes were immediately updated in the modeling tool (see below) and were thus available for the other technical partners. In the second build-evaluate cycle, we organized a workshop across all use cases to present the modeling language and tool and to demonstrate how clinical pathways can be modeled. Furthermore, we invited stakeholders to use the modeling language to define a clinical pathway and change another. Afterwards, we used a survey to investigate the need for adaptation. For evaluating the clinical pathways, we conducted a third round of interviews using a similar procedure as in the second round.

Requirement Analysis

We use a two-step procedure to derive disease-independent (first step) and disease-dependent (second step) requirements. For the first step, we use a role game across all cases to identify the information required to inform the behavior and action of the VC. The role game was conducted in Aarhus, Denmark, in

November 2018. Within the role game, the VC was played by a physician of clinic 1, while a psychologist played the patient. As the physician stems from clinic 1, we used typical scenes from the everyday life of a patient with heart failure to investigate the interaction between patient and coach and hence worked within the use case of clinic 1. Nonetheless, clinicians of all other use cases were present and discussed the results to the specifics of their use cases. Scenes of the role game comprised scheduled rehabilitation activities a patient should perform as well as potential risk situations to which the VC must respond. During the role game, the timeline was documented on a whiteboard and the types of interaction the VC has with the patient in different situations were noted. Based on this role game, we identified that typical interaction between patient and VC exhibits a process character like a general daily conversation with the coach or a chain of rehabilitation care activities (R1 in Table 1), feedback handling around a training session, and potentially hazardous situations that are indicated by evidence indicators such as safety heart rates (R2). Furthermore, we identified time events as relevant concepts that give information about a fixed sequence of activities (e.g., a medically required assessment questionnaire before doing some exercises; R6). Some target values (e.g., for medically desired durations of exercises) needed to be considered as well (R7). Also, modeling observation features in the course of detecting activities were required (R8). So, the heart rate needs to be monitored when the VC guides a patient with cardiological impairments in doing physical exercises.

For the second step, we have asked our contact persons for the three use cases to assemble medical procedural information specifying the generic procedure identified within the role game. We received textual information that adapts the more general information to the specifics of the individual use cases. Based on this information, we identified the type of information that was required to be represented within the clinical pathway and could add further disease-specific requirements. For example, we identified the need to divide different treatment chains for particular patient groups or in case of differing observed clinical parameters and create sub-pathways to keep complexity low even in cases of several sub-steps for different case scenarios (R3+4). The clinical procedures underlined the need to have not only target values for some observation features but to include a target range (e.g., there is both a minimal and a maximal desirable heart rate; R5). Table 1 summarizes the disease-independent and -dependent requirements.

After explicating the requirements, we investigated whether the requirements are met for general-purpose (*GPML*: BPMN, EPC, Activity Diagram, Flow Chart) and domain-specific modeling languages (*DSML*: BPMN4CP, BPM+). More specifically, we analyzed the semantic and syntax of each modeling language and examined whether the requirements can be mapped. As can be seen in Table 1, none of these approaches fully meet the requirements. Yet, most requirements are met for BPMN and BPMN4CP. Overall, we perceive BPMN as most promising for the vCare project's purposes for the following reasons: First, BPMN is defined as an official ISO standard and has reached a remarkable prevalence and acceptance (Chinosi and Trombetta 2012; Kocbek et al. 2015). Second, BPMN provides a well-defined meta-model formulated by the meta modeling language MOF (OMG 2011a) and facilitates model exchangeability, tool integration, and the reuse of existing modeling tools like Activiti, Bizagi, or Cubetto. Third, BPMN partly supports the derivation of computer-interpretable workflow models (OMG 2011b) and is embedded within an execution-oriented framework (Chinosi and Trombetta 2012) that is promising regarding clinical decision support systems (Yao and Kumar 2013). Finally, BPMN provides a large set of generic process modeling concepts, which implicate opportunities regarding expressiveness (Wohed et al. 2006) and an explicitly defined, lightweight extension mechanism for domain-specific extension and adaptation (Braun and Esswein 2015; OMG 2011b). Based on these reasons, we decide to adapt BPMN to meet the requirement (R1-R8).

Independent from the modeling language, requirements for integrating diverse technology and stakeholders have to be met. For example, the modeling tool needs to allow for manual adaptation of the clinical pathways by relevant stakeholders (R11), and the configuration of the modeling tool needs to enable stakeholders to do so (R12). Furthermore, clinical pathways need to allow for integrating diverse technologies such as the VC and smart-home and self-monitoring sensors. Accordingly, pathway information needs to be transformed into machine-readable code so that it can be used to set procedural precepts for the other technologies. By making use of machine learning, the pathways can also be automatically adapted (R9). Accordingly, inferences need to be made from particular effects on the patients' wellbeing or personal preferences of distinct care process's steps. After data on several single executions of those generically foreseen activities is available, these can be summatively assessed (e.g., particularly effective sub-steps in terms of a significant increase of clinical outcome measures for a relevant number of patients could be given higher priority or foreseen to a greater extent as such could be assessed as particularly and generically valuable for future care procedures). A further necessity and reason for the need

for machinal interpretability and intervention into the overall procedure is the need for personalization. The rehabilitation process is required to fit the patients' daily routines in their home environment so that the daily agenda needs to be deducible from the generic pathway (R10).

Requirements (R)		BPMN	EPC	Activity Diagram	Flow Chart	BPMN-4CP	BPM+
Requirements resulting from the role game	R1: CPs must conform to the <u>process character</u> of the rehabilitation	●	●	●	●	●	●
	R2: CPs must allow <u>exception handling triggered by evidence indicators</u>	-	-	-	-	-	-
Requirements resulting from medical information	R3: The process flow must allow the following flows: Sequential, Parallel, inclusive OR, and exclusive OR	●	●	●	●	●	●
	R4: CPs must allow for <u>subdividing</u> the pathway according to specific pathway indications	●	●	●	●	●	●
	R5: CPs must allow defining <u>degrees of freedom by target corridors</u> . These comprise the definition of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • thresholds for the designation of targets • min.-max. notation within time elements • min.-max notation indicating the number of repetitions of activities 	●	-	-	-	●	●
Requirements resulting from both	R6: CPs must allow the following <u>temporal restrains</u> : fixed time and dates, fixed intervals, defined frequency within a given time, and duration	●	-	●	-	●	●
	R7: CPs must include <u>target variables with specific values</u> for activities and time dimensions (e.g., week)	-	-	-	-	●	●
	R8: CPs must include <u>values for elements as evidence indicator</u> , resp. observation feature (e.g., heart rate)	-	-	-	-	●	-

Table 1. Requirements (Complete Support: Black Circles; Partial Support: Grey Circles; No Support: Line)

Note: BPMN = Business Process Modeling Notation; EPC = Event-Driven Process Chain; BPMN4CP = BPMN For Clinical Pathways; BPM+ = Business Process Management for Healthcare

Building The Design Artifact

We use two build-evaluate cycles in this project. In the first built-evaluate cycle, we have adapted the BPMN to fully meet the requirements. Thereby a variant, which we refer to as *BPMN4VC* (BPMN for Virtual Coaching), emerged (see an exemplary pathway template and its usage context in Figure 3). Additionally, we have designed a modeling tool (pathway editor) that allows stakeholders to update clinical pathways (e.g., if new clinical guidelines require a modification) or amend the clinical pathways for a new patient group. Furthermore, clinical pathways information can be translated into machine-readable code to enable an integration of further technologies. In the following, we describe the *BPMN4VC*, the pathway editor, and explain how clinical pathways information can be transferred into machine-readable code.

Modeling Grammar And Clinical Pathways

BPMN4VC is a domain-specific modeling language based on BPMN. Table 3 (appendix) summarizes the BPMN concepts that we adapted to the specifics of the home rehabilitation context and included in *BPMN4VC*. To meet R1, a modification has been made for the sub-process element so that activities within the sub-process can now be represented without a sequence flow. Instead, it is possible to relate the

activities via a logical operator, e.g., “any” or “at most one”. Additionally, for R1, a modification in the pathway modeler was made to link activities with service types to indicate their function in the rehabilitation process as feedback, reminder, or notification. We further changed the BPMN timer event to comply with requirements R5 and R6. It is now possible to define a timer event as an event, duration, or cycle within the pathway editor. For each timer type, attributes can be specified that are compliant with the FHIR standard (see Table 3). Furthermore, we added a new element that represents an observation feature to which a definable value can be assigned, representing a target value or threshold (R5 and R8).

Figure 3. Exemplary Pathway Using BPMN4VC Within Its Usage Context

Subsequently, we use BPMN4VC to develop clinical pathways based on the information given in the second step of the requirement analysis. In summary, we created 36 clinical pathways across three use cases. To illustrate our results, we refer to a clinical pathway of clinic 2 that treats home-based cognitive games (see Figure 3, middle). The process starts with a reminder for the game sessions as well as questionnaires and further medical assessments by the VC initializing/adapting the session of serious games. If a too risky value of the assessment scales is reached, the game can be omitted, and an e-learning session can be prompted. In this case, video material teaches coping strategies. After executing the games, further clinical assessments (e.g., questionnaires to assess fatigue and compare pre-and post-gaming values) are performed. In the case of multiple successful game executions, the game score target can be adapted to personalize the game experience (e.g., increasing the target score to trigger motivation).

Tool Support (Modeling Tool And Template Management)

Relevant stakeholders such as physicians should be enabled to work with the pathway templates that, in the end, set the procedural precepts for the whole care procedure. To allow stakeholders to do so, the pathway editor depicts the clinical pathways and allows for editing the pathway (see Figure 4). The elements available for modeling (representing the desired or possible rehabilitation procedure from the clinical point of view) can be easily chosen in a drag-and-drop manner. It is also possible to alter already placed nodes or to further link elements. The templates can be stored and exported. Also, the properties of single pathway template elements can be changed directly in the modeler. Further on, a “Template Gallery” is available to overview and browse the existing rehabilitation care pathway templates allowing the physician to easily overview, choose, alter or create the most appropriate template.

Figure 4. Screenshot Of The Pathway Modeler Tool Showing The Creation Of An Exemplary And Simplified Rehabilitation Care Pathway Template

Transitioning Clinical Pathway Information Into Machine-Readable Code

On the technical level, the template repository is implemented based on HL7 FHIR¹ enabling database persistence and REST-based access². FHIR was identified as an acknowledged standard for exchanging information in healthcare. Thus, we adopted it to be as compatible for data exchange scenarios as possible. As FHIR defines the data schema quite generically, we refined a suitable profile for the specification of the rehabilitation care pathway templates. We introduce restrictions and extensions to the base resource to map a template modeled using the editor (BPMN-XML) to the corresponding persisted FHIR resource (FHIR-XML). The pathway information is thereby shared with further components that consume and process information. The execution of the transformation of the BPMN model to the FHIR resource also changes the pathway information's degree of formality: The semi-formal BPMN model is mapped onto a formal FHIR representation, thereby allowing machinal access, understanding of the pathway information, and execution by a semantic wrapper. We investigated proper FHIR resources that can be used both for the patient-independent pathway (FHIR PlanDefinition³) and for the personalized instance (FHIR CarePlan⁴). The machinal accessibility of the pathway information allows augmenting the procedural information by data from various sensors (e.g., for indoor location detection or some vital parameters) so that further decision and personalization points can be included when automatically executing the pathway.

Evaluating The Design Artifacts

For evaluating the modeling language BPMN4VC and pathway editor, we organized a workshop to introduce the revised design artifacts. We then asked a key user of each clinic to use BPMN4VC and pathway editor to model a clinical pathway based on a textual description and adapt a given clinical pathway. By doing so, stakeholders could become familiar with the design artifacts. Subsequently, we invited these stakeholders to complete a survey using "SoSci Survey" (Leiner 2014). We asked stakeholders of the three

¹ See: <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/>

² See: <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/http.html>

³ See: <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/r4/plandefinition.html>

⁴ See: <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/careplan.html>

clinics to participate in the survey and obtained completed surveys for each use case. The survey included eight rating questions and five text-based questions distributed across five categories. The first category addresses the modeling tasks by asking participants to rate on a seven point-scale (Colman et al. 1997) how easy it was to construct/adapt a clinical pathway based on a textual description. Furthermore, we asked to rate the understandability of BPMN4VC concepts (category two; e.g., I fully understand how I can use the constructs of BPMN4VC) and to indicate whether they missed concepts for their specific use case (category three) or were confronted with redundancy (category four). Furthermore, we asked participants to rate the applicability of the pathway modeler (category five; e.g., Using the pathway modeler was easy for me). For each category, we added a question so that the participants' ratings could be substantiated with precise information on how to adapt the artifacts further (e.g., In case you had any problems, what sort of problems did you encounter while solving the modeling task and adapting the clinical pathway?).

For evaluating the **modeling language BPMN4VC**, the following results were obtained: Participants indicated that constructing a clinical pathway based on a textual description was easy for them using BPMN4VC with an average of 4.67 points (1 = fully disagree; 7 = fully agree). In contrast, they indicated that adapting a clinical pathway to a changed scenario was easy for them with an average of 6 points. In line with these results, one participant indicated that “of course it is easier to adapt the pathway rather than to build it from scratch”. For evaluating understanding of BPMN4VC constructs, participants indicated that they fully understand the explanations of the BPMN constructs with an average of 5.67 points. Further investigating understanding and difficulty of the modeling tasks revealed that most constructs “were clear to understand” although the concrete syntax of some symbols (e.g., timer event as a clock with a double circle or dashed circle) was too similar so that finding the appropriate construct was “a bit difficult in the beginning”. Yet, the participant added that after seeing some examples, differences between constructs became more apparent. Another participant supported this comment stating that “it is a matter of practice until full understanding may be reached”. Investigating whether the participants missed any constructs or experienced construct redundancy, participants stated that “at the moment, they don’t miss anything” and that “every concept seems to be useful to model the pathway for the rehabilitation of the elderly”. When evaluating the **modeling tool**, participants indicated that they were satisfied with the pathway modeler to model clinical pathways with an average of 6.67. While one participant indicated to have some problems using the modeling tool and that he would “like to have more information about the multiple options of the program” another participant “did not encounter many problems” and “found the modeling tool clear enough and simple to use once one has learned” the semantics of the constructs. For evaluating the **individual pathway templates**, the stakeholders of each use case examined their pathology-related pathways and provided requests for change where needed and additional information about the context of activities. These changes comprised mostly adding new activities or moving activities in other pathways and changing some of the default values set in the pathway, e.g., change of activity duration.

The evaluation results prompted an adaptation cycle in which activities were added to the pathways, deleted, or moved. For example, in the workshop, the stakeholders identified missing information in the pathways on their own and indicated where exactly within the process flow activities need to be added. When evaluating the new information that went along with the new activities, the need to implement new coaching service contexts and extend the initially implemented time attributes became apparent, which was modified in a second iteration step. Further changes of the pathway templates are likely in the course of their actual usage (e.g., clinicians might re-assess the appropriateness of the pathways when feedback of real patients, insights on their perceived liking, ease of use, fit with daily routines becomes available).

Discussion

In this paper, we have introduced clinical pathways as a means to set the procedural precept for integrating different technologies and stakeholders to foster home rehabilitation. Thereby, we contribute design artifacts as well as design knowledge. Our contribution to design artifacts is threefold. First, we have evolved a modeling language based on BPMN. Thereby, a variant, termed BPMN4VC, has emerged and now meets the requirements for modeling clinical pathways for the rehabilitation of the elderly in virtual coaching scenarios. Furthermore, we have designed the BPMN4VC in a way so that it now allows a proper transformation to the FHIR-standard and, thereby, allows for translating procedural information of the clinical pathways into machine-readable code. By doing so, BPMN4VC can now be used to integrate diverse technologies.

Concepts of clinical pathways		Clinical pathway usage		
(1) Modeling disease-specific information	(2) Modeling disease-independent information	(3) Integrating diverse technologies	(4) Integrating stakeholders	
Requirements	<p>R6: CPs allow the following <u>temporal restrains</u>: fixed time and dates, fixed intervals, defined frequency within a given time, duration</p> <p>R7: CPs include <u>target variables with specific values</u> for activities and time dimensions (e.g., week)</p> <p>R8: CPs include <u>values for elements as evidence indicator</u>, resp. <u>Observation feature</u> (e.g., heart rate values)</p> <p>R4: CPs allow for <u>subdividing</u> the pathway according to specific pathway indications</p> <p>R5: CPs allow defining <u>degrees of freedom</u>, comprising thresholds, min.-max notation within time elements, and min.-max notation for the repetition of activities</p>	<p>R9: Allowing adaptive clinical pathway adaptation (automatic adaptation)</p> <p>R10: Allowing to derive the daily agenda from clinical pathways</p>	<p>R11: Allowing adaptive clinical pathway (manual adaptation)</p> <p>R12: Editor + Template Gallery are required</p>	
Concrete Design Decisions	<p>R4: Physical Therapy, Pain Management, Cardiovascular Fitness, Cognitive Training, Emotional Rehabilitation, Risk Factor Modification, Pain Management, Pharmacological Intervention</p> <p>R7: Rule-based Feedback</p> <p>R8: Clinical State, Personal State, Patient-based Feedback</p> <p>(Please see Figure 5; orange concepts)</p>	<p>R1: Pathway, Pathway indication, Activity</p> <p>R2: Exception</p> <p>R6: Time Event</p> <p>R7: System Activity, Rehabilitation Activity, Feedback Activity, Goal</p> <p>R8: Patient, Patient Profile, Observation Feature</p> <p>(Please see Figure 5, grey concepts)</p>	<p><i>Semi-formal level:</i> R5,7,8: Activity, Goal, incl. threshold and parameters for sensor data</p> <p><i>Formal level:</i> R9,10: FHIR terms, JSON format</p> <p><i>Basis for machinal understanding:</i> R3,4: gateways and conditions</p> <p><i>Machinal processable inf.:</i> R9,10: choosing FHIR as an increasingly established standard allowing high interoperability</p> <p><i>Executing the VC:</i> R1,9,10: activity-based, incl. attributes that determine the VC's state</p>	<p>R12: Provision of the tool itself to model pathways on the semi-formal, graphical level</p>
Methodological Implications	<p>Data for disease-specific requirements can be collected using a method mix of analyzing documents and interviews. For analyzing documents, stakeholders can be asked to prepare documents with information that needs to be included in clinical pathways to treat a specific disease. Based on the documents, the first clinical pathways can be modeled and discussed in successive interviews with those who have provided the data.</p>	<p>Disease-independent information for VC-guided treatment can be obtained using role games with stakeholders of the project taking the role of patient, VC, and physician. Such a role game enables a common understanding of project goals and requirements and also helps to define concrete rules on how decisions can be obtained automatically.</p>	<p>It is advantageous to combine two levels of knowledge and inference capacities: First, to allow the human medical experts to model and adapt the clinical pathways to govern the overall care procedure and grasping their expertise for such procedural information. Second, to (partly) automatize the processing of the procedural precepts to enrich the VC's capacities to act as partial replacement and complement of the (absent) human caregiver. Thus, a semi-formal modeling language (here: BPMN4VC) being processable by a human modeler, plus the approach to unambiguously transform it to a standard-compliant, formal representation of the procedural information (here: FHIR) to allow processing on the machinal level.</p>	
Reuse Instruction	<p>Requirements and solutions may be reused if clinical pathways will be adapted for cardiovascular diseases, Parkinson's disease, and stroke. In case information needs to be extracted for other diseases, methodological implications can be used.</p>	<p>Requirements and solutions may be reused for VC-guided rehabilitation programs. In case a VC-guided project for a different scenario is planned, methodological implications can be followed.</p>	<p>Requirements and solutions may be reused in case several stakeholders need to adapt or define clinical pathways.</p>	<p>Requirements and solutions may be reused in case technologies are integrated into a VC-guided scenario.</p>

Table 2. Systemizing Requirements, Solutions, And Methodological Implications

Second, we have evolved a pathway editor that allows using BPMN4VC for modeling and adapting clinical pathways in a lightweight graphical manner. This editor offers a “Template Gallery” to provide an overview of clinical pathways and to alter templates. Both artifacts are in a coevolutionary relationship, meaning that an adaptation of one artifact triggers the adaptation of the other and vice versa (Schlieter et al. 2019). Third, we have evolved clinical pathways that are now used to integrate diverse technologies and stakeholders. We contribute to the design knowledge by systemizing the requirements and design decisions that we have taken to meet the requirements. Furthermore, we add methodical implications of how requirements can be specified for future projects. Also, instructions for how requirements, concrete design decisions, and methodological implications can be reused are described (see Table 2).

The requirements for designing clinical pathways for the rehabilitation of the elderly that allows for integrating diverse stakeholders and technologies are summarized in the upper part of Table 2 and are categorized into four classes. The first class, “*Modeling disease-specific information*”, includes requirements that specifically stem from our use cases including cardiovascular diseases, Parkinson’s disease, and stroke. The second class, “*Modeling disease-independent information*”, summarizes the requirements that are more generic and include requirements for modeling clinical pathways that support a VC-guided rehabilitation independent from the specific diseases. While the first two classes summarize requirements for modeling clinical pathways, there are further requirements on how the resulting clinical pathways can be used a) for *integrating diverse stakeholders* (class 3) and b) for *integrating diverse technologies* (class 4). Beyond requirements for the individual classes, Table 2 also includes concrete design decisions to meet these requirements and methodological implications that guide future researchers to investigate requirements, e.g., for other care scenarios. Furthermore, we have specified which type of information can be reused and discussed the circumstances for reusing information in the last column of Table 2. For example, if a future project aims at including other diseases into a VC-guided rehabilitation project that includes several stakeholders and diverse technologies, requirements, and concepts of Class 2-4 can be reused while requirements of class 1 need to be specified for the new diseases. In this case, we have offered methodological implications that help to specify requirements so that guidance is still available for class 1. To allow for reusing concrete design decisions of classes 1 and 2 we further contribute a meta-model (see Figure 5) that summarizes disease-independent (grey) and disease-dependent concepts (green).

Figure 5. Concepts Resulting From The Requirement Analysis From Step 1 Using The Unified Modeling Language (UML) Class Diagram

In this paper, we use conceptual modeling for deriving clinical pathways. According to (Hevner et al. 2004), conceptual models are one of the main artifacts in IS research since they are well-accepted for documenting, aggregating, and communicating IS design. However, developing and maintaining conceptual models is cost-intensive as models often need to be manually implemented and adapted in the organizational system. In the vCare project, we overcome this hurdle by following the approach to fully integrate models that serve as a backbone to enable a process-aware information system (Lenz and Reichert 2007). We call this approach a “*living model*” as the model is directly linked to the application system. Changes are directly made within the model in terms of the pathway template (by human users and AI/machine learning) and directly affect the care procedure as guided by the VC in our particular case. On top, also machine learning algorithms need to conform with the long-term rehabilitation goal as part of the automatic support measures. Therefore, a formalization and learning framework can be used for learning long-term rehabilitation goals represented by decision processes, more specifically Markov Decision Processes, which can be solved by Reinforcement Learning. This machinal inference system then acts as formalized, central storage of procedural knowledge in terms of a knowledge representation framework (Philipp et al. 2019). In this sense, the model is not only a temporary carrier of information, but a relatively stable foundation of the running IS. Particularly in areas with a high autonomy of the application system (e.g., digital assistants are interacting with citizens), living models allow for smooth adaptation and update of technology-mediated coaching. Such a change might be needed in case of new (clinical) evidence data or of shifting the context to other pathologies.

Limitations And Future Research Potential

In the vCare project, we have focused on three diseases treated as a single-use case. For each use case, we had one physician who guided us through investigating requirements, evolving a modeling grammar, and modeling the clinical pathways. Although in all use cases the physician was very experienced, acted based on clinical guidelines, and also spoke on behalf of his/her entire clinical team, we are aware that the resulting clinical pathways are not yet sufficiently evaluated, e.g., by other physicians from outside the use case context or particular clinic. This is why we plan a comprehensive evaluation detached from the use cases for the clinical pathways but also for the other design artifacts.

A second limitation concerns the role game. Although stakeholders from all use cases took part in the role game, the role game was conducted with the perspective of clinic 1 (cardiovascular diseases) so that the VC-guided rehabilitation focus may be biased according to typical processes from that perspective. We have reduced such a bias by discussing the VC-guided process for all diseases of the use cases. Also, the pathway templates were then later on added by each clinic on their own and from their own perspective. Nonetheless, further adding use cases would contribute to further evaluation and add to already discussed requirements and design decisions. To address this limitation, we invite future researchers to use the methodological guidance described in Table 2 for comparing and integrating their results to those published in this paper (grey constructs of Figure 5) so that future researchers can build on a broader basis. Such a broader basis may later on also be included in a potential reference model (Esswein et al. 2004, 2009; Schlieter et al. 2010) that can be used to derive application models for the specific diseases.

A third limitation concerns the application of the design artifacts in the patients’ home environment. So far, the design artifacts are implemented and prepared for a living-lab period, where patients are still guided in parallel also by human caregivers. An evaluation in the living-lab period also allows investigating the effect on the patient’s motivation and physiological outcomes. After completing this first living-lab test period, feedback from professionals and patients will be incorporated into the solution for the upcoming phase of testing. Then patients will be at home in a purely VC-guided environment without parallel support by human caregivers. The hurdles to applicability are correspondingly high here. Only features that have been thoroughly tested in advance can be transferred to the subsequent home environment pilot phase.

Involving different stakeholders further prompts the idea to only provide information relevant to the individual stakeholder and to shield the stakeholder from irrelevant and potentially distractive information. For example, the physicians’ primary aim is usually a treatment-related one, which purely focuses on procedural precepts for patients and their therapy. So, information used to inform the technical transformation (formal expression of decisions) may be avoided for physicians. In contrast, the avatar

designer may want to update the conversational models to set other social cues but does not need disease-specific information. Furthermore, the physician and avatar designer already gained expertise for understanding domain-related material for their domain and so may require different information than a novice model reader (Stark and Pannasch 2018). Investigating the *multi-purpose modeling approach* (Frank 2014) that allows for separating views on the different modeling levels, needs and purposes may allow handling the trade-off between required and potentially distractive information.

Limitations	Future Research Potential
No evaluation of the design artifacts independent from the use cases	Comprehensive evaluation outside the use cases for all resulting design artifacts (clinical pathways, BPMN4VC and pathway editor)
Role game was conducted from the perspective of one use case	Conducting the role game from other perspectives (e.g., other diseases) and comparing / integrating the results so that concepts pertaining to modeling scenario-specific information has a broader basis
Evaluation of the design artifacts in a living-lab with patients only from the specific use cases	Integrating and evaluating the design artifacts in a living-lab to investigate its impact on the patient's motivation and physiological outcomes
	Investigating multi-purpose modeling to allow for separating role-dependent views on the clinical pathways to handle the trade off between required and potentially distractive information.
	A setting that allows for using clinical pathways for a VC-guided rehabilitation of patients is a starting point for numerous research activities: Integrating gamification in combination with a machine learning environment to investigate the patient characteristics that are advantageous for a gamification approach OR investigating characteristics of a VC (e.g., compassion, joy) that are most helpful for patients of a certain age or with a certain disease.

Figure 6. Limitations And Future Research Potential

Having a setting that allows for using clinical pathways for VC-guided rehabilitation of patients is a starting point for further numerous research activities that can be evaluated within a patient setting. For example, integrating gamification in combination with a machine learning environment may help investigate the patient's characteristics that are optimal for a gamification approach (Schöbel et al. 2020). Furthermore, research of anthropomorphism may investigate characteristics of an even more effective or accepted VC (e.g., compassion, joy) for patients of a certain age or with a particular disease (Pfeuffer et al. 2019). Furthermore, the input device may be optimized for cognitive efficient pathway modeling (Stark et al. 2013). Limitations, as well as future research ideas, are summarized in Figure 6.

Conclusion

Prior research has investigated individual technologies such as VCs or clinical pathways. Implementing a combination of several technologies for a complex scenario of VC-guided home rehabilitation of the elderly has still been challenging. In this paper, we report about the vCare project that aims to integrate diverse technologies and stakeholders using clinical pathways to set the procedural precept for such an integration. Our contributions range from design artifacts to design knowledge. As design artifacts, we contribute BPMN4VC as a BPMN variant that can be used to model clinical pathways for the VC-guided rehabilitation of the elderly, a modeling tool that stakeholders can use to design and adapt the pathways and the clinical pathways themselves. As design knowledge we systemize requirements, concrete design decisions, methodological implications to guide future researchers for various activities such as designing a new DSML for a similar use case, adapting further diseases for a VC-guided rehabilitation as well as using clinical guidelines for a VC-guided treatment for further scenarios (see Table 2). Furthermore, we have pointed how future research may add to the design knowledge of this paper or can use the design artifacts of the vCare project to investigate research ideas of other IS domains such as the area of gamification or anthropomorphism or cognitive efficient pathway modeling.

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Appendix

Pathway Concept	Modeler Properties	Semantic description
<p>Sub-process</p>	<p>Name Sub-process</p> <p>Selection Type of Sub-Actions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Any <input type="checkbox"/> All <input type="checkbox"/> All Or None <input type="checkbox"/> Exactly One <input type="checkbox"/> At Most One <input type="checkbox"/> One Or More 	<p>A sub-process groups several activities under one scope. In the modeler, the activities in the sub-process can be assigned a type that defines the logical execution of the activities. This means that the activities are not bound to a sequence flow.</p>
<p>Service Activity</p>	<p>Name Activity</p> <p>Service Type Reminder</p> <p>Service Context Medication</p>	<p>Definition of a specific rehabilitation activity. The service type identifies the activity type. The service context specifies the kind of context.</p>
<p>Observation Feature with Goal Value</p>	<p>Observations x +</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> heart-rate blood-pressure <p>Name Heart Rate</p> <p>Default Value 120 bpm x</p>	<p>Observation feature that is associated with a task or sub-process and needs to be monitored and evaluated during execution time. Multiple observation features are selectable for one representation element as a list (e.g., Heart Rate AND blood pressure should both be monitored). Within the pathway editor, this can be supported by a drop-down menu listing all available observation features. For each observation, the definition of a default value as target or threshold is possible.</p>
<p>Timer Event - Event</p>	<p>Timer Definition Type Event</p> <p>Event mondays 2 p.m. x</p>	<p>The timer event can be defined as actual event with time and date on which a particular activity should be executed.</p>
<p>Timer Event – Duration</p>	<p>Timer Definition Type Duration</p> <p>Duration 10 x</p> <p>Maximum Duration 30 x</p> <p>Duration Time Unit min x</p>	<p>The timer event can be defined as duration attached to an activity and indicates the duration of the activity execution. It allows for the definition of minimal and maximal values.</p>
<p>Timer Event - Cycle</p>	<p>Timer Definition Type Cycle</p> <p>Frequency 2 x</p> <p>Maximum Frequency 4 x</p> <p>Period 1 x</p> <p>Maximum Period</p> <p>Period Unit wk x</p>	<p>The timer event can be defined as a cycle event. It indicates the execution frequency of an activity which can be defined by minimal and maximal values during a certain period.</p>

Table 3. Adapted BPMN Elements According To The Project Context